

Nigerian culture and globalisation: influence of TikTok video content on the promotion of Nigerian cultural values among Nigerian students

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Abstract: There have been arguments on the cultural shift to dominant Western cultural values which is eroding Nigeria's core values such as language, greetings and dressing. The invention of social media is one of the products of globalisation, therefore, this study investigated the use of Tiktok, a leading modern social media, for promotion of Nigerian cultural values in the era of globalisation and cultural imperialism among Nigerian students. Hinged on Uses and Gratifications and Cultural Imperialism theories, this study adopted the survey method, using questionnaire as instrument of data collection and focusing on undergraduate students of Adekunle Ajasin University (AAUA), Ondo, Nigeria. Using the Taro Yamaro sample size formula, 376 students were selected as the sample size while the multi stage sampling technique was adopted, using stratified, simple random, and purposive sampling techniques at different levels to select AAUA students who use TikTok. Findings revealed that exposure to video content on TikTok by AAUA students has led to cultural imperialism with many young adults imitating Western dressing pattern, eating foreign food, and adopting religious practices. However, TikTok has provided a platform to effectively promote some Nigerian language and music which in turn promote Nigerian language and music culture, thereby preserving and promoting some Nigerian cultural heritage. Based on findings, it is therefore recommended that Nigerians should leverage the social media uncensored nature to consciously showcase and preserve core cultural values by creating content that highlights, preserve and promote Nigerian core cultural values globally, mitigating cultural imperialism's impact.

Keywords: AAUA Students, Globalisation, Nigerian cultural values, Tiktok, Western culture

1. Introduction

The world today has experienced unprecedented growth driven by advancement in technology, information and communication globally, continually revolutionising the way we live and interact year after year. This is perceptible from the expanding widespread adoption and popularity of technologies like the smartphones, the Internet, satellite television, and social media especially among young adults (teenagers and youths) who found themselves in the midst of imported technology (Ajayi & Adediran, 2024). The adoption of these technologies has significantly reduced traditional barriers to global communication, fostering a more interconnected world. In recent times, African countries are facing external foreign influence from the European world which has instigated cultural conflict and cultural values clashing and imposition of foreign culture and values (Duru-Ford, 2019). Globalisation can be viewed as a process that aims to integrate and harmonise diverse cultures and beliefs, fostering global unity and understanding, but also potentially threatening the unique characteristics of individual cultures. The spread of globalisation has led to a growing concern that local cultures are being influenced and, in some cases, overshadowed by a homogenised global consumer culture. For instance, the increasing dominance of English is resulting in the gradual displacement of local dialects (Tuhus-Dubrow, 2019). Culture is a difficult term to define but can be referred to as shared values, beliefs and norms that people hold on to and their way of living which defines a particular group or community. Culture is a multifaceted concept that encompasses the beliefs, customs, traditions, language, arts, and social behaviors of a particular group of people (Wilfred, 2020). On the other hand, Cultural values represent those distinctive elements that define

people and promote unity, interaction and cooperation among people in a community with diverse religious, political, and social background and perspectives (Effiong, 2016).

For instance, cultural and religious differences have continually made some Nigerians continue to repugnant against gay or same sex marriage. The recent controversy surrounding Bobrisky's "Best Dressed Female" award at the movie premiere of a Nigerian filmmaker and actress, Eniola Ajao's movie premiere highlights the complexities of gender identity and cultural values in Nigeria. Following widespread reactions and criticism from Nigerians including prominent people such as Actress Dayo Amusa, Artist Portable and Actress Eniola Badmus who still hold onto the core values, the filmmaker had to retract the award despite her initial recognition (The Guardian, 2024). This reinforces the importance of upholding and honoring Nigeria culture, dignity and traditional gender roles.

The mass media as a result of globalisation have increasingly fostered unified global culture and unity out of great diversity in the world. The advent of the Internet has revolutionised human interactions thereby offering numerous benefits. Fair & Shah (1997) cited in Asemah et al (2013) highlight the dual nature of new media, which simultaneously promotes socio-economic progress and perpetuates underdevelopment, while also serving as a means to impose cultural and economic dominance of one system over others. However, Jeans (2019), argued that multinational companies like Coca Cola and McDonald are at the driving seat of globalisation through innovating and shaping of laws and regulations, business processes, consumption habits (eating and drinking), aspiration and dreams. Consequently, globalisation has helped limiting cultural imperialism, where there is imposition and conferral of culture and values from one economic system to another.

TikTok, a leading social media platform facilitates seamless exchange of cultural values, ideas and perspectives, breaking cultural barriers and encouraging users to share cultural norms and values in an interconnected world through their uploads of short videos on the platform. In the first quarter of 2018, By 2020, TikTok had surpassed other platforms with the greatest number of users reaching 45.8 million (Buana & Maharani, 2020). It is a micro-video sharing platform where users can create and watch usually funny, videos with various audio-visual effects and share them on the same platform and beyond (Anderson, 2020). TikTok serves as an instantaneous platform for discussion on cultural subjects and ideas thereby eliminating cultural barriers. It also provides a space for showcasing the rich cultural tapestry depicted in Nollywood films by sharing scenes featuring traditional attires, languages, music, and storytelling techniques, introducing global audiences to the depth and diversity of Nigerian culture. The platform which originated from China is predominantly used by young individuals (referred to as millennials and generation Z) and can be used to upload videos with a maximum duration of 3 minutes (Anderson, 2020).

The impact of globalisation on African culture, particularly in Nigeria, has sparked intense debate among experts. The effects of globalisation on Nigeria's cultural heritage are far-reaching and multifaceted, involving both positive and negative consequences. Globalisation can facilitate cultural exchange, preservation, and innovation, but it also poses risks of cultural homogenisation, erosion of traditional practices, and loss of cultural diversity which can lead to a disconnection from one's roots, heritage and a loss of self. As Nigerian cultural heritage faces the risk of extinction, this study investigates the role Tiktok, a leading social media platform as a vital tool for the promotion of Nigerian's traditional core values among Nigerian youths.

1.1. Statement of the problem

It is no longer news that the advent of social media have revolutionised the world, creating a global channel, where seamless exchange of varied cultural values of the world is made possible. Social media are undoubtedly one of the channels of ascertaining the effects of globalisation in the world. The world, now digitalised with everybody embracing it has encouraged countries of the world adopt the new media to drive development and to further promote cultural values and engage in global discourse (Baran, 2010). Hence, in today's interconnected world, African communities, including Nigeria have the chance to share his community cultural values and have his own values shared in the global sphere.

While developed countries effectively utilise the social media to promote their cultural values in a globalised world for sustainable development, third world countries like Nigeria may tend to see globalisation as an obstruction to their cultural and economic development. Many scholars (such as Giddens, 2010, Asemah et al, 2013) argued that social media have encouraged vices such as decadence in moral standards and cultural values by promoting vulgarity, nudity, materialism and cybercrime among youths. The Nigerian government has contemplated considered regulating social media use due to concerns about its negative impact on national identity. This consideration was prompted by the spread of harmful and valueless content by Nigerians online, which was perceived as a threat to the country's cultural values.

Although, there are negative sides of social media and globalisation, the potentials of new media, especially social media platforms in shaping social behaviour globally has been underemphasised. The relationship between globalisation, cultural values and social media has been subjected to serious communication evaluations. However, a review of the related literature revealed that there is a persistent underplay of the influence of the use of TikTok, a leading social media platform as a tool for promoting Nigerian cultural values is not adequately examined by the researchers to date. This forms the interest of this study to investigate the effectiveness of TikTok, a prominent social media platform, as a tool for promoting and preserving Nigerian culture in the face of Globalisation.

1.2. Research objectives

1. To investigate the extent AAUA undergraduate students were exposed to TikTok video Contents.
2. To examine the kind(s) of contents AAUA undergraduate students sought for on TikTok.
3. To know the Nigerian cultural values AAUA students were exposed to the most on Tiktok.
4. To find out the extent Tiktok video contents on Nigerian cultural values has promoted Nigerian cultural values among AAUA students.

2. Literature review

2.1. Conceptual review

2.1.1. Social media platforms and globalisation

Social media refer to digital communication tools that enable users to create online community, disseminate information, ideas and share personal messages and experiences (Merriam-Webster, 2017). According to Selwyn (2012), social media can be defined as applications that enable users to engage in conversations, interact with each other, create and share multimedia content, and organise and recommend existing content. They facilitate interactive personalised content creation and foster connecting with profiles of people to other people or group. Social media foster a feeling of cooperation and belonging, fostering engagement and involvement among all peoples globally. Social media has proliferated rapidly in Nigeria, mirroring the growth of broadcast stations, and continues to expand as technology advances. The past few years have seen a surge in social networking sites (SNSs), providing online platforms for people to connect, communicate, and interact (Ajayi & Adinlewa, 2020). Cohen (2011) emphasises the social and collective aspect of social media, focusing on the shift from

individualism to collaborative actions, interactions and shared experiences. Social media transcend geographical boundaries to integrate people, fostering engagement and inclusive participation in developmental issues.

Leading social media platforms are Facebook, YouTube, TikTok, Twitter, WhatsApp, Thread, etc. Facebook is a social media platform that enables users to create personal profiles, share multimedia contents, communicate and connect with others. Twitter on the other hand is a microblogging site that allows users to post concise posts (tweets) for their followers. Youtube is an online video sharing platform site where videos can be uploaded, shared and viewed while TikTok is a networking, micro-video sharing platform where users can create and watch usually funny, videos with various audio-visual effects and share them on the same platform and beyond. Whatsapp is an instant messaging platform that allows users to share of pictures, videos and messages (Anderson, 2020).

Nigerians can leverage on this accessibility and potency of the platform to share ideas and interactions with others including friends, family and diverse groups by creating contents that can showcase and preserve Nigerian cultural heritage. In creating content, a content creator has the power to create contents that resonates globally adhering to moral and ethical standards without any form of censorship. Everyone, including the youth has a mobile phone or a computer, using them to feed the social space with appealing and pleasing contents. For instance in the past, Nigerians had effectively utilised social media to drive some positive protest that captured global interest. An instance was the Boko Haram terrorists' attacks of over 200 girls in April, 2014 which prompted the advocacy group to launch the #bringbackourgirls# campaign to urge Nigerian ingovernment to act by rescuing the girls (Omoera & Ryanga (2017). Another notable example is the ENDSARS# protest in 2020 with millions of tweets and videos on alleged police brutality and extortion by Special Anti Robbery Square (SARS), a police unit in Nigeria.

The invention of social media is one of the products of globalisation. Social media literally eliminated geographical barriers of time and distance in human communication. While globalisation bridged distance by connecting the world, social media brought the world closer by creating a more intimate space where people share, interact and connect with one another. Globalisation involves creating a borderless global marketplace where countries are increasingly compelled to participate (Orunmoluyi, 2002). Globalisation aims at unifying the entire world by breaking the barrier of distances for people to exchange ideas, understand and be responsible to one another.

A global village emerges when people living in distant communities, who as a result of distance are separated from their neighbouring communities begin to establish strong ties and relationship and also enjoy positive and mutual benefits in the global world (McLuhan, 1964 cited in Baron, 2010). The process of globalisation entails that distant communities become vibrant neighborhoods nurturing close relationships by exchanging ideas, values, and innovations for a brighter future. In this age of digitalisation, many autonomous countries are increasingly being integrated into a global system of production and distribution where advanced technologies like the computer and satellite communication systems have redefined traditional media (print and electronic). Print and electronic media- newspapers, radio and television have now converged into the multimedia world in cyberspace making information universally available irrespective of their location.

Although the term "globalisation" wasn't coined until the late 20th century, its origins date back to the mercantilist era (1450-1500 AD), characterised by expanding commercial empires and growing global trade (Oni, 2018). According to Oluike (2022), globalisation refers to the worldwide integration of countries through trade, investments, economic transactions, and cultural exchange, facilitated by advances in information technology and communication, effectively creating a "global village". In relation to culture, globalisation is the process of converging different culture, values and beliefs, diminishing cultural differences and promoting a unified global system of culture and economic value system, potentially compromising traditional practices and cultural diversity in the world (Onyeonoru, 2018).

2.1.2. Culture and Nigeria cultural values

Culture is a multifaceted that can be referred to as the norms, values and practices that defines have a community's particular way of life. According to Wilfred (2020), Culture is a multifaceted concept that encompasses the beliefs, customs, traditions, language, arts, and social behaviors of a particular group of people. It refers to the totally of a community's cultural identity spanning from religious beliefs, ancestral roots of people, cultural symbols, language songs, stories, celebrations, distinctive clothing and dressing and lifestyle expressions (Asemah et al, 2013). Cultural identity encompasses a range of elements, including ethnicity, nationality, religion, and language, which collectively shape an individual's sense of self, belonging, and connection to their community and society (Ajayi & Adediran, 2024). Cultural identity is dynamic and can evolve over time, shaped by various factors such as globalisation, migration, and exposure to new perspectives, leading to a complex and multifaceted understanding of one's cultural identity (Oni, 2017).

In culture, we have those elements which is referred to as the societal values which account for morality, an important instrument to people's way of life. In a typical African community, there are some core values that are highly respected and revered. These core values are community unity, the sacredness of life, spiritual reverence, harmonious human relationship, respect for authority, and elderly ones, truthfulness, respect for own language, and punctuality among others (Onwubiko, 1991 cited in Effiong, 2016).

Language is an important aspect of culture. A language faces endangerment when younger generations are not longer acquiring the language but only with a few elderly speakers with the tendency of the it going into extinction when it is no longer spoken (Tuhus-Dubrow 2019). Globally, half of all languages is at risk of extinction and are struggling to survive with many of Nigeria languages endangered and needed to be preserved (Whalen, 2002 cited in Asemah et al, 2013). Globalisation has made English language a 'killer' language especially in counties like Nigeria while the native languages have been relegated because English Language is the predominant official language in Nigeria (Wade, 1997). As a result of being the language of globalistion and the most successful lingua franca, English, has infiltrate every aspect of modern life, from advertising to entertainment, rendering it an essential tool communication among people who are left with no choice than to speak the language. Ekhayeme (2011) as cited in Asemah et el (2013), highlighted some of the Nigerian core cultural values;

- **Age:** In the Nigerian society, age is greatly revered in Nigeria with strong emphasis on hierarchy and seniority where elderly ones are respected and admired for their wisdom, experience and longevity irrespective of the gender.
- **Social Greetings:** Socially, greetings are regarded as a sign of respect to elders. Respect for elderly is crucial in the Yoruba community. For males, it is mandatory to prostrate while females kneel to greet elders.
- **Dressing:** In Nigeria, people regard other people based on their way and manner of dressing There are other things not accepted in the Nigerian culture.
- **Language:** Language plays an high value on culture in the Nigerian culture especially when engaging with elderly ones, mindful selection of words demonstrates respect and courtesy when relating to an elderly person.

Communication is a key driver of cultural transformation and evolution. Through interactions with other cultures, existing cultural heritage can be enriched, modified, or even challenged, leading to a complex interplay of preservation, adaptation, and innovation (Hosseini, 2018). A vital social media platform for cultural promotiln and preservation is Tiktok. Tiktok is a social media platform, launched on September 20, 2016 by Toutiao as a social media platform for short music videos for everyone but actively used predominantly by teenagers. Users can select songs, create short musical videos and also update preferred videos to their TikTok

page. Generation Y and Z (teenagers and youths) have become the primary consumers of short video viewing on TikTok.

The platform facilitates the exchange of information, ideas and views, breaking cultural barriers and encouraging the sharing of cultural values in an interconnected world. Through uploads of short videos on the platform, it creates an instant platform for interactions and discussions on matters related to cultural norms and values thereby removing cultural barriers. By facilitating global interactions, TikTok has minimised cultural distances, enabling individuals from varied backgrounds to share and explore norms, values, and traditions. These potentials necessitate the focus of this study.

2.2. Social media as an agent of promoting cultural values in the era of globalisation

The media undoubtedly serves as catalysts of globalisation which entails that they disseminate diverse cultural values to the world (Effiong, 2018). However, compared with traditional media, social media as new technology has been able to facilitate the effectiveness of globalising the world by ensuring immediacy and wider reception of contents.

Despite the fact that several empirical studies have found that the social media is a potent tool employed by the West (developed countries) to culturally exert their culture on other developing countries through international mass media platforms (Burton, 2010; Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). With the positive relationship that exists between globalisation and the media, globalisation facilitates widespread promotion of cultural commodity across social, economic and political spheres (Burton, 2010). Social media is a platform where people from different countries can also upload videos related to their culture in the aspects of music, poetry, dance, local food recipes, local events, religious and national events, celebrations, national games and sports, etc. that is peculiar to particular countries This is in line with Burton (2010)'s assertion that cultural aspect of a culture such as local music can be easily accessed without any hurdle from anywhere in the world. using social media sites. Therefore social media have been a driving force for cultural promotion. Moreso, findings from previous studies have revealed that social media have helped in promoting the language aspect of a culture,

The globalisation of Nigerian culture has been significantly boosted by technology, internet, and social media, allowing Nigerian music, movies, literature, and art to reach a global audience (Oni, 2017). This increased global visibility has not only promoted pride and appreciation for Nigerian culture but also created economic opportunities for Nigerian artists and entrepreneurs, as highlighted by Ogunjimi & Abdul-rasheed (2017). Findings from Jones et al. (2013)'s study revealed that social media enabled young people Welsh local communities to promote their language by sharing and videos using their language and also connect with their friends worldwide. In recent times, rise of social media has enabled indigenous languages to break through mainstream media barrier to gain popularity and visibility (Putra, 2015; McLachlan, 2016). Social media especially Facebook, TikTok, YouTube and Instagram, videos on music, fashion, food, artefacts, songs, etc. are uploaded regularly because of their advantages of audio-text to-visual capabilities.

In as much as the use of social media has enormous advantages as a result of its open and free access to both young and old, it has also brought with it negative challenges such as violence, immorality and materialistic values. Social media influence and change people's moral and ethical values leading to increased moral decadence. The Nigerian society is characterised by hierarchy structure and respect for seniority; a non-individualistic family system and modesty in dressing pattern (no exposure of body). However, teenagers and youths now have free access to explicit nude contents and sex films, vulgar slangs and suggestive images on these platforms. Modesty in dressing is now categorised as unfashionable which is not in compliance with Nigerian culture and kneeling down or prostrating to greet an elder depending on the gender has become archaic to a young Yoruba girl/boy. Moreso, Nigerians have increasingly adopted western values by embracing the materialistic and individualistic behaviours of Western culture (Obioha, 2008 as cited in Asemah et al, 2013).

While globalisation has brought both benefits and challenges to Nigerian culture, a balanced approach that will enable Nigerian culture to thrive in a globalised world, leveraging the benefits of cultural exchange while safeguarding its unique identity and heritage should be encouraged. Therefore, this study seeks to address how social media platforms, particularly TikTok has influenced the globalisation of Nigerian cultural values.

2.3. Theoretical Review

The theoretical frameworks for this study are Uses and Gratification and Cultural Imperialism theories of mass media. **Use and Gratifications (U &G) Theory**, propounded by Katz Elihu and Blumer Jay G in 1970 is an approach to understand the uses and function of media for individuals, groups and society. The theory was first pioneered by Elihu Katz in 1959 to understand how people utilise the media rather than the impact of the media on people (Katz, 1974) cited in Okunna, 2002). Uses and Gratifications Theory proposes that media users deliberately choose content to meet their cognitive (knowledge), affective (relaxation), social (interaction), or escapist needs. Therefore, U & G approach emphasises audience's deliberate and motivation for making specific choices and highlighting both positive and negative consequences of media consumption. This is because people's needs and differences are influenced by factors such as sex, ethnicity and educational background and these needs for the purpose of satisfying these needs, beliefs and preferences (Littlejohn & Foss, 2009). This means that people do not just choose media but do so as a result of having certain ulterior motives which compel them to do so.

The relevance of U & G theory to this study is that TikTok as leading social medium where content creators create, upload, share and watch videos can be used by its users as a platform to satisfy needs of promoting indigenous culture and values. The theory helps to explain the perceived benefits of these platforms among 'Tiktokers'. People, especially young adults to create content, upload content, visit the platform and even watch video contents to acquire and get exposed to shared information regarding Nigerian cultural values.

Cultural Imperialism Theory, propounded by Schiller in 1976 is used to describe and explain the dominance of large multinational corporations, including the media of developed countries over media landscape of developing countries. It refers to the information flow on mass media from powerful countries dominates smaller nations, eroding their cultural identity and threatening local values. Asemah et al. (2017) explained that the Western-dominated media landscape imposing western cultural values and cultural norms on Africa, jeopardising the continent's cultural autonomy and unique heritage. Anaeto et al. (2018:105) summarised the cultural imperialism theory thus:

The Western countries are technologically developed in television and motion programmes. The developing countries that are not technologically developed depend on the programmes from the developed countries. This means that the programmes from the developed countries which portray their cultures will be imbibed by the developing nations (p. 105).

Since the media come from the the western developed countries and is being utilised by developing nations with their cultural values, media messages from the western countries may dominates the local cultures. Thus, this study is anchored on the media imperialism theory to examine the use of TikTok in the fate of Nigeria cultural value system in a global world or simply at the receiving end by encouraging the western culture to gradually dominate African value system.

Tables 1: The Extent AAUA Students Use TikTok

Responses	Frequency	Percentage%
Rarely	28	7.4%
Sometimes	62	16.4%
Often	176	46.8%
Always	110	29.2%
Total	376	100%

Data from table 1 above revealed a significant number of respondents use the TikTok , specifically 176 (46.8%) visit the platform often while 110 (29.2%) of respondents agreed to always use TikTok. Irregularities in frequently visiting TikTok may be attributed to some factors such as access to data, high consumption of data, power supply and phone capabilities which may limit their exposure to follow-up messages and updates on the platform.

Table 2: The level of Use/Exposure to TikTok contents

Questions	Yes	No
I often spend my leisure time watching videos on TikTok	321 (85.3%)	55 (14.7%)
I always use TikTok to post trending news and videos	75 (20%)	301(80%)
I have a lot of likes on my contents posted on TikTok	204 (54.2%)	172 (45.8)
I spend most time recording and posting videos on TikTok	121 (32.1%)	255 (67.9%)
I watch videos on TikTok to always get information	332 (88.2%)	44 (11.8%)
I select the contents I get exposed to on TikTok	251 (66.7%)	125 (33.3%)

Table 3 above revealed that majority of the respondents, specifically 321(85.3%) agreed that they often spend their leisure time watching videos on TikTok while a significant number of respondents, with 204 (54.2%) agreed to have a lot of likes on the contents they post on TikTok. Furthermore, findings showed that substantial number 75(20%) of respondents agreed that they did not spend most time recording and posting on TikTok while majority of the respondents 332 (88.2%) of respondents agreed to only watch videos on TikTok to get information regularly.. These findings revealed that majority of the respondents often watch videos on TikTok more than those that specified to only watch video Contents on TikTok.

Table 3: The kind(s) of contents sought for on TikTok

Questions	Yes	No
Entertaining contents such as funny and musical videos	341 (90.6)	35 (9.4%)
Contents promoting Nigerian cultural norms such as language, dressing pattern, etc.	179 (47.2%)	197 (52.3%)
Contents on Nigerian Politics	54 (14.3%)	320 (83.7%)
Educational contents such as tutorial videos	77 (20.7%)	299 (79.3%)
Videos on Sport activities	65 (17.2%)	311 (83.8%)

The presented data in table 3 above revealed that majority of respondents, specifically 341 (90.6%) sought for entertaining contents such as funny and musical videos on TikTok while a significant number of respondents, comprising 279 (74.2%) sought for videos showcasing Nigerian cultural values such as dressing and language.

This observation suggests that AAUA sought for entertaining contents on Tiktok the most. However, a notable number of them sought for video contents that display their Nigerian culture.

Table 4: The Aspects of Nigerian Cultural Values often shared or exposed to the most on Tiktok

Questions	Yes	No
I upload/come across contents that promote Nigerian languages on TikTok	331 (88%)	45 (12%)
I share/watch contents on TikTok showcasing Nigerian decent dress pattern	288 (76.5%)	88 (13.5,%)
I share/get exposed to Nigerian music (in Nigerian languages) or dance on TikTok	345 (91.7%)	32 (8.3%)
I upload/come across contents that promote Nigerian food on TikTok	301 (80%)	75 (20%)
I upload/watch a lot of Nigerians videos on TikTok promoting Nigerian cultural norms/ values such as social greetings including respect to elders	122 (32.4%)	258 (68.6%)
I watch/come across videos promoting Nigerian cultural norms/ values such as communal living	99 (26.3)	277 (84.7%)

Table 4 revealed that 331 (88%) agreed that they they upload/come across contents that promote Nigerian languages on TikTok. Majority of AAUA students, 345 (91.7%) identified that they share/get exposed to Nigerian music (in Nigerian languages) or dance on TikTok the most Findings revealed that the dominant aspect of Nigerian cultural value on TikTok is the promotion of Nigerian Languages and musical culture which are core Nigerian values. This indicates that young adults who got exposed to indigenous languages as well as the Nigerian musical culture may be as a result of many Nigerian artists promoting their musical videos on TikTok because of the platform being majority dominated by young adults who are their primary audience.

Table 5: The extent exposure to Tiktok contents has promoted Nigerian Cultural Values

Questions	VGE	GE	SE	LE	NE
Creating/watching Tiktok video contents makes me to value my indigenous language	126 (33.5%)	89 (23.6%)	73 (19.4%)	50 (13.2%)	38 (10.1%)
Creating/ watching contents on TikTok aids the promotion of Nigerian music culture	106 (28.1%)	109 (28.9%)	73 (19.4%)	50 (13.2%)	28 (7.4%)
Nigerian dressing pattern I see on Tiktok influence the way I dress	18 (4.7%)	26 (6.9%)	51 (13.5%)	158 (42%)	123 (32.7%)
I upload/ watch Nigeria musical videos on TikTok which promotes Nigerian culture positively	89 (23.6%)	126 (33.5%)	38 (10.1%)	52 (13.8%)	71 (18.8%)
Use of TikTok has made me to showcase and also acquire the Nigerian values and norms the more	125 (33.2%)	99 (26.3%)	31 (8.2%)	73 (19.4%)	48 (12.7%)
Creating/watching Tiktok video contents has helped in eroding Nigerian values like, morality, respect for elders and communality	95 (25.2%)	27 (7.1%)	31 (8.2%)	161 (42.8%)	62 (16.4%)

Note: VGE= very great extent; GE = Great Extent SE= Some extent; LE= Little extent, NO= No extent

Findings revealed that majority of the respondents, 215 (126+89) with 57.1% agreed that creating/watching Tiktok video contents made them to value their indigenous language to a very great extent and great extent respectively, 224 (125+99) with 58.5% agreed that their exposure to TikTok contents made them to showcase and acquire the Nigerian values and norms the more to a very great extent and great extent respectively, 215 (109+106) with 57.1% agreed that creating/ watching contents on TikTok aids the promotion of Nigerian music culture to a very great extent and great extent respectively and 215 (89+126) with 57.1% agreed to to a very great extent and great extent respectively that they upload/ watch Nigeria musical videos on TikTok which promotes Nigerian culture positively. On the other hand, a significant number of respondents 223 (161+ 62) with 59.2% disagreed to a very little extent and no extent respectively that creating/watching Tiktok video contents has helped in eroding Nigerian values like, morality, respect for elders and communality while a total number of respondents, 215 (89+ 126) with 57.1% also disagreed that Nigerian dressing pattern they see on Tiktok influence the way they dress to a very little extent and no extent respectively.

3. Research methodology

A descriptive survey research was adopted for this study with the questionnaire as the instrument for data collection. Survey method was employed for this study to generate data from a predefined group of participants to obtain people's opinions, knowledge and attitude of an issue. The research instrument used for this study is questionnaire. The population of this study consists of all undergraduates of Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba-Akoko, Ondo State which is a total of 20,000 (www.aaua.edu.ng/about-us). This category of people was specially selected for this study as they possess the relevant characteristics with which this study is concerned. This characteristic is basically that the university comprises teenagers and youths (Gen Z and millennial) who predominantly use TikTok, which is the focus of this study.

The sample size was generated using Taro Yamane formula sampling size formula to arrive at 398 respondents, however 376 copies of questionnaire were retrieved. Multi Stage sampling technique was adopted for the study to give all AAUA students equal chance of representation. First, the university was stratified unto 8 faculties in the university. Next Simple Random sampling technique was adopted to randomly select three faculties from the 8 faculties in the institution namely faculties of Arts, Agriculture and Management Science. Lastly, purposively sampling technique was applied to purposively select only AAUA students who use TikTok. TikTok was selected for this study because of its popularity and acceptability for exchange of information via musical video content thereby encouraging the sharing of cultural values through uploads of short videos on the platform.

4. Discussion of findings

The first objective of the study focused on investigating the level of exposure of Adekunle Ajasin University students to TikTok video contents. The study, therefore, gathered data through administering of copies of questionnaire to know the level at which the students upload videos on the platform. This study found that the AAUA students are aware of TikTok, use them frequently. As seen on table 1, a significant number of the respondents agreed that they used TikTok often by unloading videos or watching video contents on the platform. Therefore, findings revealed that a significant number of Nigerian University students are on Tiktok,

active on the platform and get exposed to video contents on the platform frequently. Finding from this study affirms the importance of social media platforms as effective tools for information and awareness about a phenomena across diverse sectors of life (Angus et al, 2008, Mwaura, 2014)

Moreso, another study objective of the study is to investigate the video contents AAUA students seek for on TikTok. Findings revealed that majority of respondents sought more for entertaining videos such as funny skits more than video contents showcasing Nigerian cultural values such as dressing and contents in Nigeria languages. This observation suggests a notable correlation between the use of TikTok and an increased likelihood of individuals seeking for videos displaying their Nigerian core culture.

Finding goes in line with Uses and Gratifications theory in which TikTok is a social medium where content creators can create, upload, share and watch videos and can be used by its users to satisfy their needs. The youths purposively select video contents on TikTok that will gratify their needs on getting exposed to necessary information about their cultural values. Therefore, through Nigerian cultural contents created by individuals, the youths can acquire and shape their knowledge, information regarding cultural values and identity, share post on TikTok using their indigenous language or showcasing traditional dressing pattern, music, etc. People, especially young adults upload content, visit the platform and even watch video contents to acquire shared information regarding Nigerian cultural values.

On the dominant aspect of Nigeria cultural values that is being projected on TikTok, although there are a few cultural values the youths are exposed to as indicated on the table such as language, music and indigenous dressing patterns among others, however, findings revealed that the dominant aspect of Nigerian cultural value being promoted on TikTok are the use of indigenous languages by creating and uploading contents using their indigenous languages and musical culture by composing songs in native languages which are core Nigerian values. Although, the social media is dominated by indecency in the dressing patterns of the platform users, some Nigerians youths still uphold the Nigerian core value of language and musical culture by creating contents using indigenous language or promoting his or her music through composition of songs with indigenous languages. These essential components of Nigeria's cultural heritage, reflect the country's rich diversity.

This goes in line with Ogunjimi & Abdul-rasheed (2017)'s assertion that globalisation has sparked cultural exchange and fusion, enriching Nigerian culture through the integration of global influences. This blending of cultures has given rise to innovative cultural expressions, as seen in Nigerian music genres like Afrobeat and Afrobeats, which have absorbed international styles to create a distinctive sound that resonates worldwide. Notably, Nigerian music, literature, and cinema have gained worldwide recognition and acclaim, showcasing the country's vibrant cultural diversity and creative talent (Olaniyan, 2018).

Further findings on the extent AAUA students' exposure to TikTok contents had promoted Nigerian cultural values, illuminated the significant influence of Cultural Imperialism theory revealing how powerful western countries exert powerful dominance on the weaker countries' culture like Nigeria, leading to cultural homegenisation, a process where diverse cultures become increasingly similar, leading to a loss of unique cultural identities Nigerian youths have abandoned some of their cultural heritage and has embraced the western culture and norms as theirs. Young adults in the country are embracing the foreign culture by imitation the dressing pattern, eating foreign food, dressing pattern and their religious practices as a result of their

exposure to social media platforms, particularly TikTok. This in line with Offoha & Sadiku, (1996) as cited in Asemah, (2013) assertions that Nigerians wear more of the English wears compared to the traditional attires.

Findings also revealed that TikTok has facilitated the promotion of Nigerian languages and also Nigerian music industry as many Nigerian content creators (especially the youths) watch videos using Nigerian languages or upload on TikTok using their indigenous languages. This showed that although other Nigerian cultural values are being eroded as a result of globalisation, it is graduating becoming a platform to promote indigenous languages and music. Tiktok has been able to promote Nigerian language in a global world as most Nigerian 'TikTokers' upload videos on this platform using their indigenous language. This revealed that although indigenous cultural practices are waning, Nigerian young adults remain deeply attached to their native languages, actively using them in international settings, thus sustaining a crucial link to their cultural heritage.

This is gradually making Nigerian languages to be promoted globally especially through music. This is in collaboration with Burton (2010) & Jones et al. (2013)'s findings that social media have helped in promoting the language and musical aspects of a culture. The research revealed that new media, Tiktok inclusive can be a powerful tool for promoting Nigeria's core values, fostering appreciation and pride among Nigerians for their own culture. Additionally, the diverse cultural heritage of Nigeria's various ethnic groups can be showcased through Tiktok, making it accessible to a wider audience and helping to preserve cultural diversity.

5. Implications of the study

This study revealed that exposure to video contents on TikTok by Nigerian youths has led to cultural imperialism with many young adults imitating western dressing pattern, eating foreign food, and adopting religious practices. However, through TikTok, Nigerian language and music culture have found a global stage, promoting cultural heritage and preserving traditional expression.

6. Contribution of the study

A review of existing literature reveals a significant knowledge gap regarding a leading social media platform - TikTok's influence on Nigerian cultural promotion. This study seeks to address this by investigating TikTok's efficacy as a tool for cultural preservation and global outreach. Expectedly, findings from this study will serve as a reference point for further related research works. It also provides insights for educators, policymakers, and cultural stakeholders on informed strategies for promoting Nigerian cultural values in the digital age.

7. Recommendations

Based on findings, the study recommends that the new generation (teenagers and youths) should be continually use and maximise the potentials of the platform by getting exposed to contents that resonates to Nigerian moral and ethical standards and those reminds them of their roots, history and style of living. Also, by holding tenaciously to Nigerian culture, the youths should consciously promote their culture by uploading video contents that will showcase the richness of Nigerian culture to the world. Although Tiktok platform has been a vital tool for promotion of Nigerian language and music, other core cultural values of the country such as dressing, food, etc. should also be encouraged and showcased on the platform too by digitising archival materials, creating online repositories of cultural artifacts, and using the platforms to showcase Nigerian culture to a global audience. Lastly, Nigerian authorities and young adults should maximise the advantage of TikTok as an open source, free- posting, decentralised channel where content creators can consciously create contents that will popularise their indigenous heritage and culture in the age of globalisation.

8. Conclusion

Findings from this study revealed that Tiktok is a conduit for cultural imperialism, enabling the possibility of cultural shift from Nigerian cultural standards, contributing to cultural homogenisation. This study therefore concludes that infiltration of technology and globalisation has led to significant changes in Nigerian society's values and cultural norms. To an extent, its use has paved way to promoting some aspects of Nigerian culture such as promotion of Nigerian language and music. Also, although, the media serves as a significant channel for learning, it is also responsible for the proliferation of harmful trends among youths including pornography, drug addiction, dressing, gangsterism, rape, etc. Based on the findings of this study, the paper concludes as a result of globalization, embracing the Western culture is gradually eroding Nigeria's cultural values as the new generation of the country have little regard for their local culture except that of indigenous language and musical culture; rather, they value the foreign culture.

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